

Theoretical prediction of brittle-to-ductile transition of bio-inspired nacreous composites

Cui S. K., Lu Z. X. and Yang Z. Y.

Institute of Solid Mechanics, School of Aeronautic Science and Engineering,
Beihang University (BUAA), Beijing 100083, China

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Outline

1

Introduction

2

Theoretical Analysis

Governing equations and boundary conditions

Prediction of elastic modulus

Prediction of transition of failure modes

3

Numerical validation

4

Conclusions

Introduction

Theory

Experiment

Simulation

Methods

Jager I, et al. Biophys. J, 2000.

Begley M R, et al. J. Mech. Phys. Solids, 2012

Gao H, et al. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci, 2003.

Wei X, et al. Acs Nano, 2012.

F. Barthelat, et al. Exp. Mech, 2007

L. Djumas, et al., Nat. Publ. Gr. 2016

S. Askarinejad, et al, Compos Struct. 2018

R. Mirzaeifar, et al, ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng. 2015

D. Sen, et al, Sci. Rep. 2011

Zhang Y, et al. J Mech Behav Biomed Mater 2012

L.S. Dimas, et al, J. Mater. Res. 2013

L.S. Dimas, et al, Bioinspiration and Biomimetics. 2012

Mechanical properties

Physical properties

Ballistic properties

Contents

I.J.W. Pro, et al, J. Mech. Phys. Solids. 2015

S. Askarinejad, et al, Int. J. Plast. 2018

H. Yao, et al, Compos. Sci. Technol. 2013

Z.Q. Zhang, et al, J. Mech. Phys. Solids. 2010

Yang W, et al. Compos Struct 2019

P. Zhang, et al, J. Mech. Phys. Solids. 2015

P. Zhang, et al, J. Appl. Mech. 2013

Flores-Johnson EA, et al. Compos Struct 2015

Flores-Johnson EA, et al. Compos Sci Technol 2014

Gu G X, et al. Extrem. Mech. Lett, 2016.

G.X. Gu, et al. Adv. Mater, 2017.

Introduction

Currey J D .
Proc.soc.lond.
b, 1977.

2000
Staggered

Tension-shear chain (TSC)

$$\frac{1}{E} = \frac{4(1 - \Phi)}{G_p \Phi^2 \rho^2} + \frac{1}{\Phi E_m}$$

Gao H, et al. PNAS, 2003.

$$J_c = w \int \sigma(\epsilon) d\epsilon$$

Gao H , et al. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2003.

$$\sigma_{critical} = \begin{cases} \phi \sigma_{critical}^p \frac{\rho}{2\rho'_{critical}}, \\ \phi \sigma_{critical}^p \frac{1}{2}, \end{cases}$$

Zhang Z Q , et al. JMPS, 2010.

1977: Nacre

$\Phi =$	0	0.40	0.40	0.40
$E' =$	1	2.40	7.25	59.0
$\epsilon'_{max} =$	1	0.40	0.10	0.04
$\sigma'_{max} =$	1	0.97	0.70	2.30

Jager I, et al .
Biophysical
Journal, 2000.

2003

Kotla S P , et al. CST. 2000.

2008

Bertoldi K , et al. CST. 2008.

2010

Wei X, et al. Acs Nano, 2012.

2012

Begley M R , et al. JMPS, 2012.

Brick and mortar (BM)

#ICCM22

Introduction

BM

TSC

Brick
Mortar

Theoretical analysis

Geometric relationship

$$\begin{cases} u_1(l-x) + u_2(x) = \Delta \\ \delta u = u_2(x) - u_1(x) \end{cases}$$

$$\delta u = \Delta - u_1(l-x) - u_1(x)$$

Combining Eqs. (1)-(3)

Shear stress in the mortar

$$\tau_M = \frac{\delta u}{h_M} G_M \quad (1)$$

Normal stress in the brick

$$\sigma_B = E_B \cdot u_1'(x) \quad (2)$$

Equilibrium equation of the brick

$$\sigma_B \cdot t \cdot h_{BR}/2 = (\sigma_B + d\sigma_B) \cdot t \cdot h_{BR}/2 + \tau_M \cdot dx \cdot t$$

$$\rightarrow \tau_M = - \left[\frac{h_B}{2} \cdot \frac{d\sigma_B}{dx} \right] \quad (3)$$

General assumptions:

- i) The horizontal mortar is in the pure shear stress state.
- ii) The vertical mortar is in the uniaxial tensile stress state.
- iii) The bricks are in the uniaxial tensile stress state and the transverse stress is ignored.
- iv) Both the mortar and the brick are regarded as the linear elastic perfectly brittle constitutive model.

Theoretical analysis

BM

TSC

Boundary conditions:

$$u_1(0) = 0 \quad u_1\left(\frac{l}{2}\right) = \frac{C}{2}$$

$$u_1'(l) = 0 \quad [1] \quad \times$$

$$u_1'(l) = \frac{E_c}{\Phi E_B} \frac{2[\Delta - u_1(l)]}{l_c} \quad [2,3] \quad \checkmark$$

$$u_1''(x) = \frac{2G_M}{h_M h_B E_B} [u_1(l-x) + u_1(x) - \Delta]$$

Where:

$$E_c = \begin{cases} \frac{E_M}{1 - \nu_M^2} & \text{for plane stress} \\ \frac{E_M(1 - \nu_M)}{(1 + \nu_M)(1 - 2\nu_M)} & \text{for other cases} \end{cases}$$

Governing equation and a particular solution:

$$u_1''(x) - \frac{4G_M}{h_M h_B E_B} u_1(x) = 0 \quad u_1^0(x) = \frac{\Delta}{2} - \frac{C_1}{2} \left(\frac{l}{2} - x\right)$$

The general solution:

$$u_1(x) = A_1 \exp(x/\lambda) + B_1 \exp(-x/\lambda) + \frac{\Delta}{2} - \frac{C_1}{2} (l/2 - x)$$

Φ is the volume fraction of the bricks.

- [1] Yao H, Song Z, Xu Z, et al. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2013, 81(Complete):24-29.
- [2] S. Askarinejad, and N. Rahbar. *International Journal of Plasticity*, Vol. 107, pp 122-149, 2018.
- [3] M. H. Sadd. "Elasticity: theory, applications, and numeric". 3rd edition, Waltham, MA:Academic Press, 2014.

Theoretical analysis

BM

→ Δ

← Δ

TSC

→ Δ

Stresses distributions in mortar and brick

Shear stress in horizontal mortar:

$$\tau_M(x) = \frac{G_M \Delta}{h_M} \frac{\cosh(2\mu x/l - \mu)}{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

Normal stress in the brick:

$$\sigma_B(x) = \frac{E_B \Delta}{l} \frac{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu - \mu \sinh(2\mu x/l - \mu)}{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

Recall boundary conditions:

$$u_1'(l) = \frac{E_c}{\Phi E_B} \frac{2[\Delta - u_1(l)]}{l_c}$$

The normal stress in vertical mortar:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{E_c}{\Phi} \frac{2[\Delta - u_1(l)]}{l_c} = \frac{E_B \Delta}{l} \frac{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu}{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

Displacement function for the brick #1, and It would be reduced to the form in Ref. [1] when $l_c \rightarrow \infty$:

$$u_1(x) = \frac{\Delta}{2} \frac{1}{2R l/l_c + (1 + \mu \tanh \mu)} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(2\mu x/l - \mu)}{\cosh \mu} \right] + \frac{\Delta x}{l} \frac{2R l/l_c + \mu \tanh \mu}{2R l/l_c + (1 + \mu \tanh \mu)}$$

Where: $\mu = \frac{l}{2\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{l^2 G_M}{h_M h_B E_B}}$ $R = \frac{E_c}{\Phi E_B}$

Theoretical analysis

Prediction of Elastic Modulus

The effective stress of the composites:

$$\sigma_t = \left[\sigma(0) \cdot \frac{h_B}{2} + \sigma_c \cdot \frac{h_B}{2} \right] / h_B = \frac{E_B \Delta}{l} \frac{2R l / l_c \cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu}{2R l / l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

The effective elastic modulus of the composites:

$$E_t = E_B \frac{2R l / l_c \cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu}{2R l / l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

The normalized effective elastic modulus of the composites:

$$E'_t = \frac{2R l / l_c \cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu}{2R l / l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

Displacement function for the brick #1:

$$u_1(x) = \frac{\Delta}{2} \frac{1}{2R l / l_c + (1 + \mu \tanh \mu)} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(2\mu x / l - \mu)}{\cosh \mu} \right] + \frac{\Delta x}{l} \frac{2R l / l_c + \mu \tanh \mu}{2R l / l_c + (1 + \mu \tanh \mu)}$$

When $l_c \rightarrow \infty$
reducing to

$$u_1(x) = \frac{\Delta}{2} \frac{1}{(1 + \mu \tanh \mu)} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(2\mu x / l - \mu)}{\cosh \mu} \right] + \frac{\Delta x}{l} \frac{\mu \tanh \mu}{(1 + \mu \tanh \mu)} \quad [1]$$

[1] Yao H, Song Z, Xu Z, et al. Composites Science and Technology, 2013, 81(Complete):24-29.

Theoretical analysis

Prediction of transition of failure modes and initial tensile strength

Failure strain of the composites:

$$\varepsilon_t^y = \min(\varepsilon_f^{HM}, \varepsilon_f^B, \varepsilon_f^{VM})$$

Initial tensile strength:

$$\sigma_t^y = E_t \varepsilon_t^y$$

Rupture of horizontal mortar

$$\tau_M(x) = \frac{G_M \Delta}{h_M} \frac{\cosh(2\mu x/l - \mu)}{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

$$\varepsilon_f^{HM} = \frac{\Delta}{l_B} = \frac{\tau_M^y h_M}{G_M l_B} (1 + \mu \tanh \mu + 2R l_B/l_c)$$

Rupture of brick

$$\sigma_B(x) = \frac{E_B \Delta}{l} \frac{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu - \mu \sinh(2\mu x/l - \mu)}{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

$$\varepsilon_f^B = \frac{\Delta}{l_B} = \frac{\sigma_B^y}{E_B} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \mu \tanh \mu}{2R l_B/l_c + 2\mu \tanh \mu}\right)$$

Rupture of vertical mortar

$$\sigma_c = \frac{E_B \Delta}{l} \frac{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu}{2R l/l_c \cosh \mu + (\cosh \mu + \mu \sinh \mu)}$$

$$\varepsilon_f^{VM} = \frac{\Delta}{l_B} = \frac{\sigma_c^y}{E_B} \left(1 + \frac{1 + \mu \tanh \mu}{2R l_B/l_c}\right)$$

Theoretical analysis

Prediction of transition of failure modes and initial tensile strength

In S1 model, the maximum shear stress in horizontal mortar and normal stress in brick could be written as:

$$\tau_M^1 = \frac{G_M l_c}{2RE_B h_M} \sigma_M^y \quad \sigma_B^1 = \left(1 + \frac{\mu \tanh \mu}{R l_B / l_c}\right) \sigma_M^y$$

In S2 model, the relationship between shear stress in horizontal mortar and normal stress in brick is:

$$\sigma_B^2 = \rho \tau_M^2$$

If horizontal mortar is supposed to fail by taking: $\tau_M^2 = \tau_M^y - \tau_M^1$

then the ultimate failure event could be determined by stress ratio

$$R_{HMB}^{TSC} = \frac{(\tau_M^1 + \tau_M^2) / \tau_M^y}{(\sigma_B^1 + \sigma_B^2) / \sigma_B^y} = \frac{\sigma_B^y}{\sigma_M^y} \frac{1}{1 + \rho + \frac{\mu l_c}{R l_B} (\tanh \mu - \mu)}$$

Superscripts 1 and 2 represent the “S1” and “S2” model.

#ICCM22

After the rupture of vertical mortar

Numerical validation

Geometric Parameters

l (mm)	h_B (mm)	l_c (mm)	h_M (mm)
3.75	1.5	0.08	0.08

Material Properties

Material	E (MPa)	ν	σ_s (MPa)
Brick	100000	0.3	100
Mortar	100	0.49	20

Mesh and multi-unit sensitivity

Numerical validation

Models used to calculate the stiffness

Models used to predict different failure modes

$$\rho = 2l/h_B$$

$$l_c = 0.08 \cdot \rho/5$$

Flow chart of the UMAT in the FEM calculation

Numerical validation

Shear stress in horizontal mortar

Normal stress in the brick

Numerical validation

Prediction of initial tensile strength and transition of failure modes

In the plane strain state

$$\varepsilon_t^y = \min(\varepsilon_f^{HM}, \varepsilon_f^B, \varepsilon_f^{VM})$$

$$\sigma_t^y = E_t \varepsilon_t^y$$

$$\sigma_t^y = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma_M^y}{2} \left(2 + \frac{\mu \tanh \mu}{R l_B / l_c} \right) \\ \frac{\sigma_B^y}{2} \left(1 + \frac{R l_B / l_c}{R l_B / l_c + \mu \tanh \mu} \right) \end{cases}$$

Conclusions

Therefore, some important conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- ◆ The effective elastic modulus of the composites using the BM model is similar to that using the TSC model in plane stress state, and a large discrepancy can be observed between them in plane strain state.
- ◆ The vertical interface plays a decisive role in the toughening mechanism of the nacreous composite by extending the deformation process from one stage to two stages.
- ◆ The stiffness and initial tensile strength of the composite are optimized when an optimal brick size is adopted for given material parameters.

THANKS!

- PhD candidate of Institute of Solid Mechanics,
- Beihang University (BUAA), Beijing, 100083, China
- E-mail: kkangtdrink@163.com

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22